

Creare Mediterraneus

searching the roots in a digital way

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Abstract: *Creare Mediterraneus* is a project developed by Economia Creativa Consultancy¹, spin-off from ‘Reinventing Costa del Sol Through Creative Tourism’ project. It aims to encourage social innovation through exchange of ideas and creative thinking, harnessing new ways of developing the synergies between art, culture, economics and technology in order to find solutions to the challenges that the Mediterranean -and Humanity- is facing: immigration, inequality, global warming, mass tourism, unemployment, lack of perspective for youth, to cite some of them.

The aim is to raise awareness among local entrepreneurs, artists, creative people, humanists (philosophers, anthropologists, historians) and policy makers about the opportunity of creating new ways of working: multifunctional, multi-sectorial, multicultural and multinational mixing creativity, economy, culture, art and technology for their development and the development of the Mediterranean Region in a sustainable and innovative way.

Creare Mediterraneus is an online platform for the Creative Economy² in the Mediterranean Region promoting the networking, exchange and dialogue among entrepreneurs, artists, cultural managers, museums and cultural institutions, public authorities and other actors.

We aim to contribute to the international debate for developing an alternative economic system considering creativity, people and the environment at the center of it. The #CulturalEra

Keywords: creative economy, digital platform, entrepreneurship, social innovation, training and coaching, youth empowerment

XV. INTRODUCTION

This paper aims to present *Creare Mediterraneus*, a platform for boosting creative economy in the Mediterranean region however, first it is important to briefly describe the context in which this project has been conceived.

Nowadays, the Mediterranean region faces many challenges both in the North and in the South side. It is a heterogeneous and culturally diverse area, although with cultural, economic and historic interrelation and heritage.

In the North side, particularly in Spain, Italy and Greece, aging population, lack of perspective for young people, high youth unemployment (figure 1), brain drain, the financial crisis, migration, tourism seasonality and difficulties to adapt to the new way of living, working and producing as a consequence of

¹ www.economiecreativa.eu

² UNESCO 2013, Creative Economy Report: Widening Local Development Pathways

the Information Communication Technologies (ICT) and its impact in the economic and social model are the main challenges.

In the South, the Arab Region³ suffers from scarcity of resources, low development levels, one of the highest percentages of youth in the population in the world and of youth unemployment (figure 1), migration and brain drain and internal conflicts implying that many people have to abandon their homeland, becoming refugees many of them, and migrate to other countries, often to the European Union, recently mainly to Germany.

Source:

France, Italy, Spain, Greece and Turkey: OECD, Youth not in employment, education or training (NEET), age 15-29, (2013)

Egypt, Jordan, Palestine and Tunisia: NEETs rate among young people age 15-29, (2012-2013) / Report: 'THE CHALLENGE OF YOUTH EMPLOYABILITY IN ARAB MEDITERRANEAN COUNTRIES, THE ROLE OF ACTIVE LABOUR MARKET PROGRAMMES'

Morocco: Unemployment rates in youth population age 15-24, (2013) Report: 'THE CHALLENGE OF YOUTH EMPLOYABILITY IN ARAB MEDITERRANEAN COUNTRIES, THE ROLE OF ACTIVE LABOUR MARKET PROGRAMMES'

Figure 1. Unemployment/NEET percentage rate in the Mediterranean Region

As we see, both sides of the Mediterranean basin face multiples challenges, however the high youth unemployment rate, the lack of perspective among young people and brain drain due to the migration mainly to Central Europe, UK and Nordic Countries are common in both sides.

In this context, the traditional economic model, for example in tourism⁴, has proved insufficient to create the opportunities that young people and society need: the ecosystem and the culture that can enable business creation and innovation to flourish in the digital age. New economic sectors such as the creative economy that has proved resilient to the global recession have to be developed⁵. *Creare Mediterraneus*, a spin-off from *Reinventing Costa del Sol Through Creative Tourism*⁶ project by Economía Creativa

³ Yusuf Mansur in *Creativity, Innovation, and Development*, 2015, reviews the Doing Business and Competitiveness indicators in the Arab Region

⁴ Maxime Weigert 2012, *The Challenges of Tourism in the Mediterranean Region*

⁵ *The Economic Impact of the Creative Industries in the Americas*, a report prepared by Oxford Economics for the British Council, IDB, OAS

⁶ A.C. Ruiz Soria, J.E. Molendowska (2014), *Reinventing Costa del Sol Through Creative Tourism*

Consultancy included at OECD LEED Forum on Partnerships and Local Governance⁷, aims to contribute to the development of a more creative, innovative and entrepreneur Mediterranean Region by promoting entrepreneurship culture, providing training, showcasing entrepreneurs projects, accelerating start-ups, mentorships, open calls for young artists, creating a network of hub organizations in the whole region and beyond for the dissemination and co-creation of activities.

XVI. Why an online platform for boosting creative economy in the Mediterranean Region?

The Mediterranean basin faces many challenges, however we can ask ourselves why an online platform for boosting the creative economy in the Mediterranean basin?

The Mediterranean Region is rich in art, traditions, cultural heritage, history, gastronomy, has a particular notion of time, a lifestyle, and to sum up, a cultural identity⁸.

Creative Economy: The term refers to the socio-economic potential of activities that trade with creativity, knowledge and information. Governments and creative sectors across the world are increasingly recognizing its importance as a generator of jobs, wealth and cultural engagement. At the heart of the creative economy are the cultural and creative industries that lie at the crossroads of arts, culture, business and technology.

Source: British Council 'What are Creative Industries and Creative Economy'

http://creativecities.britishcouncil.org/creative-industries/what_are_creative_industries_and_creative_economy

Figure 2.- Creative Economy: Definition

According to UNESCO (2013), 'Culture is a driver of development, led by the growth of the *creative economy* (figure 2) in general and the *creative and cultural industries* (figure 3) in particular, recognized not only for their economic value, but also increasingly for the role in producing new creative ideas or technologies, and their non-monetized social benefits. Culture also enables development. It empowers people with capacities to take ownership of their own development processes'. 'When interventions in fields such youth engagement takes the cultural context into account, transformative and sustainable change can occur.' And that is exactly what *Creare Mediterraneus* aims: the transformation of the Region into a creative place, a creative destination, a creative reference in different fields: film, music, creative tourism, arts and crafts, cultural heritage, etc. Empirical data proves that the creative economy is underdeveloped, especially in the Arab countries⁹, but not only. Therefore there is a potential for

⁷ [http://www.oecd.org/leed-](http://www.oecd.org/leed-forum/database/localdevelopmentprojects/spain_reinventing%20costa%20del%20sol%20through%20creative%20tourism.pdf)

[forum/database/localdevelopmentprojects/spain_reinventing%20costa%20del%20sol%20through%20creative%20tourism.pdf](http://www.oecd.org/leed-forum/database/localdevelopmentprojects/spain_reinventing%20costa%20del%20sol%20through%20creative%20tourism.pdf)

⁸ Affaya Rim 2009, *Unity and Diversity in Euro-Mediterranean Identities: Euro-European and Arabo-Mediterranean Dimensions*

⁹ Najib Harabi (2009), *Creative industries: case studies from Arab countries*

developing creative economy in the region, including the regeneration of the tourism industry into a creative tourism business model¹⁰.

Creative Industries - 'those industries that are based on individual creativity, skill and talent with the potential to create wealth and jobs through developing intellectual property'
Includes thirteen sectors: advertising, architecture, the art and antiques market, crafts, design, designer fashion, film, interactive leisure software (ie. video games), music, the performing arts, publishing, software, and television and radio.

Source: British Council 'What are Creative Industries and Creative Economy'
http://creativecities.britishcouncil.org/creative-industries/what_are_creative_industries_and_creative_economy

Figure 3.- Creative Industries: Definition

It can still be asked why an online platform? Very few will have nowadays doubt that in the digital age in which we live value is created through networks and platforms¹¹. The website and social media allow almost free international transactions particularly of ideas, the raw material for creative economy. Platforms provide the opportunity of multi-sectorial, multifunctional and multi-generational interactions among different stakeholders in a constant relation that leads to peer to peer learning, exchange of best practices, added value contributions to existing projects, connecting ideas to create new visions and projects, dialogue, space for cultural diplomacy and a forum for discussion within a sector, creative economy in our case. In consequence, platforms and networks allow the creation of value and projects from bottom-up, generating more inclusive and sustainable output. Platforms normally are composed by a large number of stakeholders and users-producers of content what it generates a multiplier effect for dissemination of results and for the branding of the project itself.

In the Arab countries, the southern side of the Mediterranean Basin, according to *The Arab World Online 2014*:

Trends in Internet and Mobile Usage in the Arab Region report by Mohammed Bin Rashid School of Government, 20% of the internet users who responded to their survey were unemployed, 33% used English as language of preference while using internet, almost 80% has at least a university degree or higher level of education. Following ITU World Telecommunication report, in 2013 77% of Europeans households have access to internet and 34% in Arab countries where internet household penetration has grown annually by 15% between 2009 and 2013. This figures show a positive scenario for developing an online platform to empower people's knowledge, skills and competences.

¹⁰ A.C. Ruiz Soria (2014) *ibid*, describe the application of the creative tourism business model to Costa del Sol, Spain

¹¹ For more insight about platform economy, see M.Kenney and J. Zysman discussion paper (draft), 2015, *Choosing a Future in the Platform Economy: The Implications and Consequences of Digital Platforms*

XVII. Creare Mediterraneus: searching the roots in a digital way

Creare Mediterraneus is an online platform for boosting creative entrepreneurship in the Mediterranean Region. It was conceived by Economía Creativa Consultancy in order to apply for the NICE – Network for Innovation in Culture and Creativity in Europe- Awards 2014¹², the competition consisted in solving a social challenge through an innovative project using digital technology. The Mediterranean symbolizes the *roots* of many civilizations, values, beliefs, attitudes, a lifestyle, a diet -recognized by UNESCO as immaterial cultural heritage¹³- acquired and share through generations. The Mediterranean is *culture*, the very source of creativity and creative industries as we have seen above. In consequence, in order to solve the numerous challenges that the Mediterranean region faces, it is needed to search these roots in a digital way by boosting creativity.

Creare Mediterraneus is designed to develop and strengthen the links among creative people, artists and innovators in the Mediterranean Region by online interaction, combined with onsite training and a forum for discussions. It aims to stimulate the exchange of good practices within creative economy, to impulse the exchange of ideas, collaboration, internationalization of audiences, showcase of art works and projects.

Creare Mediterraneus is a catalyst for creativity and innovation in the Mediterranean beyond its geographic borders. One of the key objectives is to brand the Mediterranean Region as a *creative space*. Despite the great cultural heritage and cultural potential of the Region, it is not identified yet as a creative place, due, among other reasons, to the fact that the majority of its visitors are tourists who search for resort type of holidays, sun and beaches. However even this *traditional* touristic model is showing clear signs of stagnation or even crisis, generating seasonality problems such as congestion, pollution and poor quality temporal jobs that lead to regular periods of unemployment.

At the moment, *Creare Mediterraneus* consists:

1. A web/blog, www.crearemediterraneus.wordpress.com (figure 4), whose aim is to clearly explain the project –in English, although with the collaboration of volunteers we can implement content in other languages-, showcase entrepreneurial projects in the creative industries and host a blog/news section for discussions and exchange of best practices

Figure 4.- Creare Mediterraneus Web/blog

¹² <http://nice-europe.eu/>

¹³ <http://www.unesco.org/culture/ich/en/RL/mediterranean-diet-00884>

2. Facebook Page –although other social media such as Twitter will be added- in which disseminate the platform content, projects and activities, interact through more informal debates and build a network of fans and active followers (<https://www.facebook.com/crearemediterraneus/>, figure 5)

Figure 5.- Creare Mediterraneo Facebook page

Creare Mediterraneo has the following *objectives*:

- Boosting creative & digital economy in the Region
- Promote entrepreneurship culture and support young entrepreneurs and start-ups
- Provide trainings on key competences for entrepreneurship and creative economy
- Branding the Mediterranean Region as creative space
- Develop an active network of stakeholders to create value, dialogue and cultural diplomacy
- International cooperation and projects development
- Mapping the creative economy and creative industries in the Mediterranean basin
- Promote the *Mediterranean lifestyle* through art, creativity and innovation

How will *Creare Mediterraneo* work in practice?

Creare Mediterraneo Platform implies the participation of multiple stakeholders (figure 6) in a cloud way, actively interacting with each other in order to exchange ideas, create value, develop projects, disseminate results, evaluate activities, identify needs and design solutions to transform creativity into *innovation*.

The main stakeholders will be *young people, creatives & artists* who will benefit from the trainings, the opportunity of interacting with international organizations, youth associations, institutions, etc., and the support for establishing and promoting their start-ups or social entrepreneurship projects. *Hub organizations*, for example cultural foundations, development agencies, NGO, international institutions or government bodies, have an important role in order to disseminate the projects, collaborate for the organization of trainings, events and fora, contribute to funding activities/projects or facilitate the access to alternative funding (crowdfunding, donations, etc.).

Figure 6.- Creare Mediterraneus Platform & Stakeholders

Creare Mediterraneus *activities* cover different areas (figure 7):

Figure 7.- Creare Mediterraneus areas of activity

- 1) *Projects/Entrepreneurial Start-ups*: The platform is initially a web/blog in which young people aged 18-35 years old preferably –although it is also open to the participation of people from other age groups if their projects are related to youth empowerment- can showcase their entrepreneurial ventures on the website simply by sending an email with a project picture/logo, a brief description in English and links to the social media of the project/entrepreneurial venture. It will be uploaded on the web by *Creare Mediterraneus*' team. Once critical user base is reached or enough financial means raised, a log-in system will be implemented in order to facilitate self-management for each project's microsite.

- 2) *Crowd-innovation and training.* Creare Mediterraneo will offer entrepreneurs, SME, start ups, public authorities, NGO, artists and creatives trainings, coaching and co-creating experiences through focus groups and workshops to develop experimental and hybrid research methodologies with a holistic approach building knowledge in a crowd way, from bottom-up, through multidisciplinary and multisectorial perspective developing public-private partnerships. It is essential the collaboration of Hub organizations and financial support from public grants, sponsorship, participants fees and/or public subsidies, in order to deliver trainings mainly -but not only- for young people to develop competences such as:
 - a. Self-management, personal branding
 - b. Team building
 - c. Project development
 - d. Funding, alternative funding and crowdfunding
 - e. Pitching and presentation skills
 - f. Social media, storytelling and marketing strategy
 - g. Business planning
 - h. Internationalization
 - i. Creativity development and innovation
- 3) *Accelerator and Mentorship Programme.*
 - a. *Accelerator:* An annual open call will be published for entrepreneurial projects and start ups within Creative Industries that will receive personalized support and mentorship services for accelerating their development. Advice will be provided to the selected start-ups for accessing to seed finance and business angels or for organizing crowdfunding campaigns.
 - b. The *Mentorship* programme will be in an ongoing basis and open to professionals with key expertise in creative industries, digital economy, entrepreneurship, innovation and international cooperation who would like to work *pro-bono* to help the development of young people in the Mediterranean region through practical advice, strategic thinking, leads, etc.
- 4) *Art open call:* an annual call for original artworks *inspired* by an annual *theme* related to the *Mediterranean* will be organized for young artists from the Mediterranean Region to present their works. The selected artworks and projects will be curated and exhibited in *Creare Mediterraneo* web/blog and its social media.
- 5) Through *Innovation Camps* (Social/Business) we offer intensive 2 to 3 days workshops where entrepreneurs, SME, public authorities, creative people, students, etc. are presented with a innovation challenge (about any aspect: business, social, cultural, development, etc.) to generate businesses/case models to solve it.

Creare Mediterraneus will be funded as shown in figure 8:

Figure 8.- Creare Mediterraneus funding sources

There are numerous grants and international programmes for which digital platforms for boosting creative economy such *Creare Mediterraneus* can apply: the Creative Europe from the European Commission¹⁴, the UNCTAD Creative Economy Programme¹⁵ or the British Council Creative Economy programme¹⁶ among others.

We expect to count for this project with civil society participation through donations, business angels to support creative entrepreneurs and crowdfunding campaigns for particular actions such the annual forum. Institutional or commercial sponsors will be an important source of funding for *Creare Mediterraneus*, however all sponsors will have to align to our mission and *ethos*.

Fees from participants in trainings and workshops will be other source of funding for Creare Mediterraneus although participants in unemployment or other exclusion situation will be exempted of any payment for the trainings or activities.

Being *Creare Mediterraneus* a platform, a network of networks, it has to rely in partnerships and solid and long lasting relationships with hub organizations in the different countries and regions of the Mediterranean basin. Their contribution to the project's funding can be directly –by covering the expenses for some of the trainings or workshops- or indirectly by contributing with their premises or assisting to the organization and delivery of *Creare Mediterraneus* operations as well as in the dissemination of the results (which it has an unvaluable implicit cost if accounted as marketing and promotion).

¹⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/programmes/creative-europe/index_en.htm

¹⁵ <http://unctad.org/en/Pages/DITC/CreativeEconomy/Creative-Economy-Programme.aspx>

¹⁶ <http://creativeconomy.britishcouncil.org/>

XVIII. CONCLUSION

The Mediterranean basin is facing many challenges. Traditional development models have proved insufficient to find solutions, as we have seen in the case of tourism. Therefore, *Creare Mediterraneus* aims to provide a new platform for the development of creative and digital economy in the region, harnessing creative entrepreneurship particularly among young people, mapping creative industries and branding the Mediterranean region as a creative place. In order to achieve this ambitious objective, we seek to build a solid international network of stakeholders (hub organizations, investors, partners, volunteers and collaborators) to contribute to *Creare Mediterraneus* platform and disseminate its vision: searching the Mediterranean *roots* in a digital way.

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